

Management

CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR TOWARDS ONLINE SHOPPING

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ABSTRACT

With the increasing internet literacy, the prospect of online marketing is increasing. There are millions of people online any time and they all are a potential consumer in the online market. Since there are so many providers, the most important thing for organizations is to understand what are consumer wants and needs in this competitive business environment. Customer buying behaviors are influenced by different factors such as culture, social class, references group relation, family, salary level and salary independency, age, gender etc. and so they show different customer behaviors. These studies explain online shopping important and consumer buying behavior in online shopping.

Keywords:

Online shopping, Consumer Buying Behavior Influences of Online Shopping Decision.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The internet has played a significant role in our daily life in that people can talk through the internet to one who is actually on the other side of the Earth, can send email around the clock, can search information, can play game with others, and even can buy things online. Meanwhile, Internet shopping has been widely accepted as a way of purchasing products and services. It has become a more popular means in the Internet world ((Bourlakis et al., 2008)). On the other hand, some consumers still feel uncomfortable to buy online. Lack of trust, for instance, seems to be the major reason that impedes consumers to buy online. Also, consumers may have a need to exam and feel the products and to meet friends and get some more comments about the products before purchasing. Such factors may have negative influence on consumer decision to shop online.

Buyer behavior of consumers plays one of the key roles for fulfillment of the main goals of a

company. It is influenced by many external and internal factors but the company can also influence the final process of buyer decision-making process significantly by its activities.

2. ONLINE SHOPPING

Due to technological innovations, the traditional way of shopping has become insufficient for individuals. Individuals now prefer easy ways to reach brands and stores and it can be said that 'The Internet has fundamentally changed customer's notions of convenience, speed, price, product information and service. As a result, it has given marketers a whole new way to create value for customers and build relationships with them' (Kotler and Armstrong, 2012; 532).

E-commerce provides consumers more choices, more information and more ways to buy. Moreover, e-commerce will remain as a medium to sell products, services and content over the internet (Korper and Ellis, 2001; 1). As a result individuals can buy or sell anything, 'at anytime, from anywhere through online shopping' (Ko, et al., 2004; 20).

3. ONLINE SHOPPING AND CONSUMER BEHAVIOR

With the emergence of the Internet, Internet-based electronic commerce developed and this environment provide individuals to reach information about products and services easily. Moreover, commercial organizations have moved to incorporate the World Wide Web into their promotional campaigns, and by offering the facility of online purchasing and like many other innovations 'online shopping' has become a part of our lives.

Furthermore, the Internet business have created more competitive environment, understanding features of online shoppers' behaviors have been more important. Moreover, it should be analyzed by online sellers that 'why some still prefer not to buy online'. perceived characteristics of the web sale channel which include risk, advantage, online shopping experience, service quality, trust; second category is web site and product characteristics which are risk reduction measures, web site features and product characteristics; and the last category clarified by authors is consumer characteristics. Consumer characteristics are driven by various types of features. Consumer shopping orientations, demographic variables, computer, internet knowledge and usage, consumer innovativeness and psychological variables.

4. FACTORS THAT AFFECTING CONSUMER BEHAVIORS, CONSUMER CHARACTERISTICS IN THE ONLINE MEDIUM

Consumer behaviors can be explained in four dimensions which are personal characteristics, psychological characteristics, social characteristics and cultural characteristics.

PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS

Characteristics of a person, is an important factor affecting the purchase decision process. Personal factors include age, gender, occupation, income status, education, life style.

Both gender group gets familiar with using the Internet .Men are more familiar with using technology and their interest is bigger than women. In today's world this gap started to decrease and it has found that 'an increasing number of women use the Internet' they also found that men

are claimed to be more pragmatic whereas women are more anxious by the time they face new things. It has emerged that demographic factors such as gender are significant factors when people face new things. In this case, their attitudes have been driven by their social environment.

Furthermore, individuals with lower income tend to approach online shopping activity more cautious and find this medium as a riskier place since their tolerance for financial losses are lower with respect to consumers with higher income.

On the other hand it has found that 'online shoppers are not necessarily more educated'. Online shopping has been considered as a easy activity, therefore education level has not a big effect on it. However educated people are more likely to accept innovations easily educated level may have an effect on decision process.

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Online consumers psychologically deal with themselves and they frequently questioning themselves. Motivation make consumers to ask themselves, should they look a better price or should they shop online more often and these kind of questions. Perception is one of the important factors and makes consumers examine the security of the web site or the quality of the product. In this case the seller organizations have to be successful in terms of providing customers a confidence. Another psychological aspect is personality. The personality factor may drive consumers to ask themselves what kinds of web sites are best suited for their personal preferences. Personal preferences manage consumers to decide. The fourth one is attitude and attitudes can change easily, therefore marketers are many interested in these features. Consumers try to find out what they like or not in respect to a particular situation. The last factor is emotion; they may consider their last experience. Consumers are affected by choices and emotions alter with the experience of their choice.

SOCIAL CHARACTERISTICS

The social influence comes from the reference groups. For the online consumers reference groups are identified as virtual communities, consisting of discussion groups on a web site. Other people's experiences, opinions have shown in this medium and affect consumers. Another one are contact links, web site links related to the product or the service, which make individuals ensure about the decision. Family is one of this reference groups. There are different ways that reference groups influence an individual's attitude, they may expose a new behavior or life style or may create a pressure to accept the attitude.

CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS

Different social classes create different behaviors. Consumers from lower social classes would not have the same properties such as higher intention to buy or higher probability like higher social classes. Furthermore, culture set values and beliefs in the early ages therefore person's wants and needs are driven by this setted feature. Almost everything we do; how we give and receive information, make decisions, lead and manage, working teams, use time is influenced by

culture. Culture as 'the collective mental programming of the mind which distinguishes the members of one group or category of people from another'.

CUSTOMER LOYALTY

In the last century, technological advances leading to very large changes on marketing. Consequently it offered new opportunities and also led to even greater competition they are facing. This makes businesses to leave classical management mentality and to adopt new business and market strategies. The internet, which becomes a part of daily lives, also becomes a part of everyday shopping. To retain customers, who are just a few keystrokes away from any web sites without any constraint, has become very difficult. In case of any dissatisfaction, these customers would prefer a high number of competitors and the switching cost is almost absence, thus in online environment, e-stores is to make it even more important to ensure customer loyalty.

Products of technology and informatics start to change the customers' shopping behavior, as it changes many habits of them. In online shopping, customers have some expectations from companies before shopping, as in traditional shopping. To satisfy or dissatisfy this expectations or how extent of satisfaction is achieved create the perceived value of customers. Satisfaction or dissatisfaction occurs as depends on experiences which exist after online shopping. This situation affects the trust to company. Customers' loyalty or disloyalty depends on how much these factors are achieved.

TRUST

Consumers' trust to a provider or supplier results with becoming committed to the company. Trust issue is exceed with a few successful transactions, after individuals start feel safe and believe that this supplier answer their needs and wants. On the other hand provided information is another issue in terms of online shopping. Since online shopping is an activity which related to a computer-system, individuals cannot touch or feel products. Therefore their decisions based on the information that provided by online retailer. Information issue not only important in terms of availability situation, it is also important in convenience and personalization concept. Web site design, access to information, access time to information also influence on behaviors of consumers.

Without the online purchasing channel, all those operations would be more costly on the physical effort and time perspective, and moreover it would not be possible for the customer to reach requisite information about the product and to compare it with the most of the competitors. As being advantageous for firms and customers, online sale technology is accepted by the firms while not accepted sufficiently by the customers. At this point, users' buying behavior over internet should be analyzed.

Influences of Online Shopping Decision:

- Motivations that lead consumer to buy online
- Convenience

- Web design
- 24 hours access
- Brand browser segment
- Price visibility
- Internet speed
- Cash on delivery
- Free home delivery
- Quick search
- Better service
- Easy payment
- New design
- Trendy shopping
- Saves travel time
- Availability
- Trustworthy
- Website security
- Detail information is availability
- Searching the products easy
- Take less time

5. SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION

For factors that affect consumers while shopping online, and that affect satisfaction, they consider that convenience, and trust are the most important variables, the next which are important for them are prices and quality of products. Those variables are the most essential ones for consumers when they decide to shop online.

Also, according to results, if there is a good consumers previous experience, if consumer is satisfied with products and services, and if there is risk at minimum level than he will buy more in the future, which means he will be loyal. Web design and delivery time are not important for consumers while doing online shopping purchases.

Online shopping is getting popularity in the young generation such as students and professionals. Students usually prefer to buy goods from its original source and they mostly prefer online shopping.

When a consumers to make purchases online to buy something, he or she is affected by assorted factors. The main Influencing factors have been identified as, price, confidence, security, convenience, time, after sale service and discounted deals. The price factor exists because the prices are often lower through online shopping as compared with physical purchases in the market. Buy online can be of great benefit to the consumer in terms of convenience, saving time and money.

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